

Emotional education in post-pandemic times: emerging needs and educational response

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 has provoked a rapid adaptation in the post-pandemic period, posing a great challenge for all areas, particularly education. This paper presents an action-research study in a Spanish educational institution, aiming to determine the emotional impact that COVID-19 has left on primary school students, with special attention to students with specific educational needs (SEN). In addition, the aim was to articulate a proposal for improving emotional education addressed at school. As a result of this study, the socio-affective needs of the pupils and the benefits of psychomotricity and artistic education for strengthening emotional development have been discovered. As a result, an innovative project has also been proposed for educational guidance and tutoring at CPEIPS La Salle La Laguna, based on the programming of cross-cutting units in various subjects to optimize the socio-emotional and psychomotor development of the students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A case study is presented, applied in an educational center in Tenerife, Canary Islands, at the CPEIPS La Salle La Laguna, where a problem related to the deficiencies and insufficiencies of the emotional education model being addressed in the school was posed in the post-pandemic era. The objective was to understand how emotional education and the new socio-affective needs of the students in the classroom were being worked on, and specifically, how the cases that presented more vulnerability, with special educational needs (SEN), were being attended to after the period of the health crisis. All this with the ultimate aim of drawing lessons to improve the educational response offered and providing a new, more inclusive proposal capable of enhancing the emotional competence of “all” the students after the pandemic.

The situation that the world has gone through due to COVID-19 is a historical fact [1], [2] that forced extraordinary measures to be taken in many areas that affect daily life [3]–[6]. The educational sector was significantly affected, undergoing a radical change in the organization of schools [7] and an adaptation to the new reality by the entire educational community [8], which brought about the transition from a face-to-face model to a virtual model [9]. Regarding the existing literature, different studies have explained that the forced adaptation of teachers during the health crisis revealed their shortcomings in terms of training and the necessary strategies to intervene online; it highlighted difficulties in their instructional models in terms of attending to all areas of children’s learning, especially with the most vulnerable [10]–[15]. As a consequence, the socio-affective development of all students was quite diminished, with greater deficiencies being perceived in the most vulnerable population that presented SEN [16]–[24].

According to previous studies [25], [26], in recent decades, there has been a consensus in recognizing, both at the level of research and educational policies, that promoting social and emotional well-being should be an essential part of inclusive schools. With this new post-pandemic context, starting from the idea that school is full of socio-emotional experiences [27]–[30], an urgent need has been revealed to analyze and improve classroom work around emotional education. Establishing a new approach focused on developing socio-emotional skills for life is urgent to promote children's well-being [31]. COVID-19 has highlighted the gaps in this regard and the urgency of implementing new ways of educating and structuring these improvement proposals in the reality of specific school practices to make them genuinely inclusive [32]. That is why it is a priority to study how these gaps are reflected in each school context, specifying the new needs that arose in emotional education for “all” in the post-pandemic. Only by starting from an analysis of the school response to the latest emerging socio-affective needs can projects for improvement and educational innovation be proposed, which contemplate the emotional education of all students, especially children with SEN. It is not enough to analyze the footprint of COVID-19 and draw lessons for improvement, as is being done in most research on the problem; it is urgent to study what has happened in each school in a particular way and build a contextualized improvement proposal that defines how to improve the emotional education of all the students in the center and, especially of the children with SEN. This work offers this research for action, thus promoting the transfer of the lessons learned after the pandemic. Emotionally educating involves promoting tolerance and understanding towards others, empathy, and worrying about creating a safe and welcoming learning environment with healthy and positive interpersonal relationships [33]. Such education is also understood as “an educational, continuous, and permanent process, whose purpose is to enhance the development of social competencies as an essential element in the integral development of people to equip them for life” [34]. Learning requires experiencing and living the process associated with emotions and feelings derived from a positive emotional experience, so emotions play a fundamental role in teaching-learning processes [35].

To build improvement and innovation processes along these lines, attention must be paid to the psycho-pedagogical organizational and curricular dimensions. Regarding the first, various authors consider that the construction of intelligence and affectivity is linked to bodily and motor experience [36]–[39]. At the base of expression and communication is the body, which needs to combine emotions with actions to know how to manage them. “Thanks to the body and movement, as axes of educational action, our brain develops” [37]. Along these lines, the psychomotor intervention experienced within the school places each child at the center of the learning process, always conceiving them as a global being (union of the motor, affective, and mental). This is achieved through activities that favor motor expressiveness and movement within a stimulating environment, with experiences promoting significant relationships with oneself, others, and the environment [39]. Regarding the organizational and curricular dimension, preventive intervention must be facilitated by the different educational agents, from a proactive, collaborative approach focused on curricular orientation processes and educational action. This approach has been considered fundamental for improving emotional education in educational centers [40], [41].

To contribute to the urgency of reviewing the model and scope of emotional education and inclusive care for “all” students in various school contexts after the pandemic, in this case, a study was conducted in a school at the primary education stage. The evident needs could guide the type of intervention designed to improve the school's emotional education. An intervention adapted to the post-pandemic situation was intended, a historical moment that significantly limited physical interaction between people. A systematized and cross-sectional reinforcement of emotional education was proposed through different learning situations that favored the development of socio-emotional competence based on creative expression and psychomotor practice. An inclusive educational innovation for primary education was designed that could be permanently implemented in the educational institution. The innovation was based on a program of activities integrated into the different curricular subjects and from a cross-sectional approach. The main recipients of this innovation program were “all” primary education students. However, families were also involved, thanks to the culture of collaboration intended to be reinforced in the center.

The innovation proposal is contextualized in the La Salle La Laguna school, an educational center of primary education located in the second most important city on the island of Tenerife, with which contact was maintained for six months, and this period occupied the development of the study and the project described in this work. However, this experience regarding emotional education in primary education students, especially students with SEN, could be considered for implementation in other similar centers that also suffered the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. This approach has been feasible thanks to the support system and involvement of the centers that have promoted and focused on the new educational reality from the collaborative work model.

La Salle La Laguna school is located on the island of Tenerife. It is a charter school with more than 623 students, of which 278 are in primary education (66 students have some SEN: autism spectrum disorder (ASD), attention deficit disorder with or without hyperactivity (ADHD), down syndrome, and maturity delay). According to the Educational Project of the Center (PEC), the socio-educational reality of the

students is very diverse; to attend them, the school has a staff of 40 teachers, in addition to the Guidance Department, which includes a psychologist, psycho-pedagogue, pedagogue, and therapeutic pedagogy. Special attention is given to the HARA project (interiority program: the way to oneself, to others, and transcendence) related to emotional education to show the educational community a path toward the search for emotional balance.

In Spain, it was on March 14, 2020, that a state of health alarm was declared (Royal Decree 463/2020) [42] caused by COVID-19. This event represented the most significant educational challenge in recent decades [43]. The educational agents had to assume responsibilities, which were unknown until then, in a climate of high uncertainty. With this new situation, the emotional impact on students increased the need to work transversally and continuously on socioemotional aspects, especially with students with SEN [44]. In a study carried out in 2020 by the University of Barcelona, with 1,087 non-university teachers in Spain to know the emotional experiences, needs, and concerns derived from this crisis [1], to the question “What emotions have you detected that the students have experienced?” The teachers indicated that their students mainly experienced fear, sadness, uncertainty, and unpleasant emotions. It is known that all emotions are necessary for survival; it is essential to understand their effects, especially if they are intense and prolonged excessively over time, since the absence of adequate emotional management can jeopardize the quality of life of those who experience them.

COVID-19 in education generated a significant disruption that affected almost 1.6 billion students in more than 190 countries worldwide. In some countries, this led to a rethinking of education school content and pedagogical culture to meet new social needs and demands, among which the management of emotions stood out. A report [45] warned that public administrations should prioritize emotional education to mitigate the effects of the pandemic [1]. However, what about students at these early ages? How do males and females deal with emotions in the face of COVID-19, and how do students who require a specific educational response express their feelings? [1].

Before COVID-19 pandemic, there was already interest in including emotional intelligence in the classroom [46]–[48], a demand supported by many international reports that indicated emotional development as one of the challenges of the future [49], [50]. Including emotions in both teacher training programs, the curriculum, and tutorial action was recommended throughout all educational stages [51]. However, it has been, especially during and after the pandemic, when sufficient evidence of the value of emotional education in the educational environment, especially with SEN students, has been generated [1]. It was found that during the pandemic, people were locked up. With them, the expressions of affection were limited in a way imposed by social distance, weakening essential elements of the social relationship such as words, face-to-face, and emotions [52]. Therefore, due to COVID-19, it became urgent to prioritize measures for developing emotional education in the educational community [53], particularly with primary education students and especially with those with SEN. It is considered essential to include in the curriculum the development of competencies related to the premise of learning to “be a person” and to “live together,” thus favoring the improvement of attitudes towards oneself, towards others, and school [54].

It has already been shown that emotional education favors learning and improves students’ self-esteem and empathy, forming more competent and successful people [55]. The benefits of social and emotional learning programs have been demonstrated in seven relevant areas, including developing social skills, reducing antisocial behaviors, and improving mental health [56]. Recent contributions from neuroscience have made it possible to better understand the brain’s functioning of emotions.

Some branches, such as cognitive neuroscience, offer specific contributions that facilitate understanding these processes. The need to understand neuroplasticity processes and the impact of emotions, physical activity, and social contexts on learning arises. As a new discipline, neuroeducation proposes to take these contributions from the neurosciences to improve educational practices and thus optimize meaningful learning in school contexts [57]. At present, as stated by Forero *et al.* [58], it is of utmost importance to “describe the theoretical contributions of neuro pedagogy to the development of didactic strategies in teaching-learning in a postcode 19 era.”

According to Medero *et al.* [59], in the Canary Islands, emotional education was implemented under the name of Emotional Education and Creativity (EMOCREA), in the curriculum of primary education from 1st to 4th grade in 2013 to develop the emotional and creative aspects of the curriculum elements. Despite this, it is curious that teachers ask for more training to manage emotions and to be able to emotionally accompany their students and their families, as well as to know strategies or resources that can help them in emotional accompaniment [1], [54], [60], [61]. Studies such as these claim the need to introduce values education and incredibly emotional education in the curricula of all educational stages, considering it as one more competence to be developed in a curricular and transversal way, adjusting it to the contents of the various areas of knowledge. The new educational law in Spain, LOMLOE (organic law on amendment of the organic law on education, Law 3/2020, de 29 December) [62], reinforces the work of emotional and values education and

enhances meaningful learning for the development of transversal competencies responsible for the development of autonomy and reflection.

González-Herrera *et al.* [54] affirmed that art and its expression serve as tools for transmitting the very essence of each person, favoring a more significant emotional development [63]. Working in the different areas of psychomotor skills, play, and the stimulation of expressiveness in general is essential. This promotes children's emotional and socio-affective development and the affective and cognitive maturation in the formative processes in a way that allows them to consolidate learning meaningfully. This is supposed on the part of teachers to develop empathy, body listening, and the ability to respect each person's natural expressiveness and rhythm [51]. In previous decades [64], a reference was made to the need to "rethink education." The need to go beyond conventional academic learning was highlighted, giving tutoring and emotions a fundamental role, taking the idea of integrating into education four fundamental pillars for life: learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, and learning to live together, on which a humanistic vision of education is based [65]. All approaches converge toward the essence of what becomes an educational model sensitive to emotions and the ability to manage them properly.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Methodological approach

To gain in-depth knowledge of the perception of the center's educational community members at the primary education stage, a case study was carried out on the needs and shortcomings of the training process in emotional education implemented in the center. This study would be the basis for designing an innovation and inclusion program in contextualized emotional education. This program's shared, collaborative construction had to be justified by analyzing some critical elements of emotional education developed by the center during COVID-19, thus detecting the needs felt and expressed by the participants in this regard. Consistent with this, a mixed methodological approach was used to carry out this study; given the nature of the study itself, this type of approach was considered to be the most suitable since it implies more excellent proximity and more direct interaction with the participants, thus enabling access to their ideas, beliefs, ways of acting, feeling and perceiving [48].

2.2. Objectives

The objectives to be achieved in this study are:

- To know the opinion of the management team, the guidance counselor, and the teaching staff on how COVID-19 has affected primary education students, specifically students with SEN.
- To inquire about the degree of teacher training in emotional education.
- To find out whether emotional education is worked on in the different subjects in a cross-cutting manner in the primary education stage.
- To assess the center's professionals' vision regarding how psychomotor skills, corporal expression, and artistic education can favor emotional expression.

Of particular interest were the objectives related to how various primary education professionals of the school were trained in emotional competencies. It was of particular interest to detect the center's needs based on what its professionals could explicitly state, thus specifying perceived and felt weaknesses, threats, strengths, and opportunities in relation to emotional and socio-affective education in their center. On this basis, a project of innovation and inclusion in emotional education could be designed to be coherent with the needs shared by the educational community.

2.3. Sample

The study's sample was purposive and convenient. The participants who took part in the study represented the various governing, coordinating and guidance and tutorial action bodies. Specifically, the participants were the school principal, the primary education coordinator, the school counselor, the psychomotor education teacher and the 13 tutors of the six grades from first to sixth grade of primary education (a total of 17 members of the educational team).

2.4. Data collection techniques and instruments

2.4.1. Semi-structured interview

This type of interview allowed us to inquire about the opinions of the director, the stage coordinator, the guidance counselor, and the psychomotor education teacher of the center. The questions were established according to the study categories and following the following scheme:

- Questions referring to children's emotional and socio-affective development during the pandemic, especially SEN students.
- Questions on the educational action of primary school tutors to address emotional and socio-affective development after confinement, especially with SEN students.
- Organizational issues at the center level regarding the processes planned to address the emotional education and social-affective development of “all” students in the primary school stage.
- Questions about new organizational and pedagogical strategies that are alternative and viable in the current situation for implementing actions that promote the emotional and socio-affective development of “all” students in the primary school stage.

2.4.2. Participant observation

Participant observation provided the opportunity to share and live the experiences in the context of the educational community. This made it possible to obtain real-time data within the daily environment of the students by observing how their tutors interacted with them. A standard record sheet was developed for all the courses observed according to the categories of the study, which was also consistent with the questions contemplated for the elaboration of the interviews.

2.4.3. Ad hoc questionnaire

As seen by primary school teachers, an Ad hoc questionnaire was developed on the needs, importance, weaknesses, strengths, and threats of emotional and socio-affective education. The test was then content-validated; three judges, experts in emotional education, and two professionals from the center evaluated the final version. It consists of 11 questions (2 multiple-choice and nine open questions).

2.4.4. Procedure

During four months (February to May 2021), information was collected from the different informants for subsequent analysis. The interviews were conducted in person and the environment of the educational center (La Salle La Laguna school). The non-systematic participant observations were carried out throughout the term and were structured to collect data from all the primary classrooms on several occasions. Finally, the questionnaire was created in an electronic version (Google Forms), facilitating the participants' responses. A descriptive statistical analysis of the responses was carried out.

Once the information was collected, the responses from the interviews and notes from the observations were coded and categorized. This step, which was crucial for an adequate treatment of the information to answer the questions of the study, took the form of a coding process, according to each type of informant, following the following scheme: Director (DIR), primary education coordinator (COORPRI), guidance counselor (ORI), relational psychomotrician (PSICO) and TUTn (where TUR is tutor and “n” the number of the participant). For the analysis of the information, the data collected were linked to the categories of the study through data triangulation. As Pérez [48] points out, this procedure allows more excellent quality control in the study process and guarantees validity, credibility, and rigor in the results achieved. In line with these authors, a multiple triangulation was chosen, combining two or more types of triangulations to use more than one level of analysis: methodological, data, and observer triangulation. Table 1 shows the categories into which the analyzed data were grouped and their definitions.

Table 1. Definition of the categories

Categories	Definition
Influence of the pandemic on emotional and social-affective development in students. Teacher training in emotional education.	Includes data on how the pandemic has affected students' emotional and social-affective development. It refers to the level and type of emotional education training teachers have.
Importance of the transversal treatment in the classroom.	It addresses the importance of emotional education in the rest of the primary education subjects in a cross-cutting manner.
Importance of psychomotor education, art education, and corporeality for expressing emotions.	It refers to the value placed on the principles of psychomotor education, artistic education, and physical education in promoting children's socio-affective development.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main results are presented about the objectives of this study. It was intended to know the most pressing needs in primary school education about the emotional development of students, especially those with SEN. These data would allow us to focus on and outline the treatment of socioemotional competence in

post-pandemic schools. Based on this study, it was possible to design a project of innovation and inclusion in emotional education based on what the community perceived as a priority to be addressed in this area.

Regarding the opinion of the management team, the guidance counselor, and the teaching staff on how COVID has affected the students of primary education, and specifically, the students with SEN, the results obtained show the following:

“It has been determined that, on the one hand, although there is still no scientific data and, therefore, no demonstrable data, there is some apprehension and fear regarding the attendance back to school and compliance with the measures that were adopted by the pandemic situation.” (DIR)

In addition, it was stated that:

“Although the confinement had a positive side, it also had a negative impact as it broke unexpectedly with the routine of the children, which caused a problem in their emotional and socio-affective development, leaving it very impaired.” (COORPRI)

“The acceleration for a new paradigm, which was already underway, but with the pandemic has worsened, it has been stated that it has affected, and much, hence the need to implement such a change in education.” (ORI)

Also, as stated by tutors from 1st to 6th grade of primary education, and as we have been able to gather in the observations,

“There are many children with fear, some of them addicted to video games, Tik-Tok, which makes them lack contact with other children, in a stage of maximum social and emotional learning.” (TUT5)

Finally, about students with SEN and their socio-affective, emotional, and expressive difficulties, variability was observed in the responses to the questionnaire since 44.4% of teachers considered that students with SEN do have more significant challenges in socio-affective and emotional development, 33.3% thought that they do not, and 22.2% did not take a position since they alluded to arguments related to:

“The type of difficulty and context they have at school and family level.” (TUT4)

On the other hand, referring to the degree of training in emotional education presented by the teachers, the following results were obtained: 88.9% had received such training through the HARA project developed at the center, while 11.1% had no training in emotional education. From the observations, it was possible to detect that this training did not seem to be sufficient to address specific situations that arose in the classrooms in the post-pandemic period since, on many occasions, an adequate response was not given to deal with the stress manifested by some students, especially in cases where they had SEN.

About whether emotional education is worked on in the different subjects in a cross-cutting manner, the results obtained stated that:

“Now these competencies are worked on horizontally, from seminars to projects. The aim is always for the child to exemplify, transmit their feelings, share experiences in a cooperative team, solve their conflicts and thus lay the foundations for good emotional tools.” (TUT3)

However, from the observation, it could be seen that this is not entirely true because when they were in subjects such as Spanish language and literature, more importance and weight was given to the contents and knowledge of this subject and not to emotional education itself, if a conflict arose in the classroom, they tried to cut it and continued with the subject, they did not stop to reinforce and reflect on the values or feelings about it. When faced with conflictive and compromising situations, students with SEN showed exaggerated emotions and lacked the skills to face and manage them. Finally, mentioning the vision of the professionals of the center regarding the influence of psychomotor skills, body expression, and art education on the expression of emotions, it was stated that

“Play is essential for the development of children because through it, as it involves being in contact with their peers, it can be determined whether they have any emotional difficulty or not.” (PSYCH)

Likewise, 100% of teachers considered it fundamental, confirming that, as tutors, knowing the students in all their facets is necessary to promote their self-knowledge and preparation for unexpected or essential situations in their educational lives.

These results allow us to provide arguments about how, within the post-pandemic school, different types of deficiencies were perceived in the students' socio-emotional coping, as evidenced after returning to face-to-face classroom teaching. This coincides with previous research [58] stated about this post-pandemic era, proving that people are relearning how to function in society and even how to learn. These authors argue that, for this reason, education is the first institution to face the new era. As this study shows, despite the efforts of teachers, the didactic models do not match the socio-affective gaps revealed in the aftermath of the pandemic. This aligns with the findings of several research studies that demonstrate the need for a more profound and longer-term system transformation. They call for improving the school that considers the time, capacities, and resources needed to foster pedagogical relationships [22], where internal and external resources are adapted to individual and collective socio-cultural and emotional characteristics [12].

Emotions such as fear, bewilderment, stress, and anxiety surfaced strongly, highlighting the emotional deficiencies of students to cope resiliently with the new situation. This study, as in others [1]–[6], shows the extent of the impact of psychologically stressful situations, such as COVID-19, on children and adolescents. As these authors state [5], many studies have shown that fear of contagion hindered social contact and interpersonal relationships. For this reason, it is essential to strengthen and redirect the new emotional education in schools [48], [51], as can be seen from the study results. As in their documentary review state [47], for some time, there has been “scientific evidence on the benefits of emotional intelligence in the school environment, showing its relevance in health and happiness, school coexistence or academic performance of people.”

This has led to various models of emotional education for the development of emotional intelligence. However, in most cases, this has not resulted in obtaining a comprehensive proposal for emotional education with applicability in school practices [35]. As a study points out [66], it is still unclear how emotional education is to be implemented at the different levels of the educational system because no clear guidelines are described for it. The centers that, like the one in this study, had opted for emotional education programs often did so from self-taught experiences that, after the pandemic, made evident the insufficiency of its scope in the school.

The results obtained in this study show that the priority of teachers after the health crisis continues to be the development of subjects and the instructional dimension of their teaching function, leaving the approach to emotional education in the background. The focus continues to be on transmitting curricular content rather than the relational dimension that fosters authentic and holistic learning and full inclusion. In the post-pandemic, according to previous study [67], not only a digital gap was revealed, but also a learning and school gap, affecting more children in vulnerable situations. For these cases in particular, returning to school was a delicate moment that required teachers to make an effort to reconstruct the situation experienced, return to learning in schools, and “re-engage students, taking into account all the differences that may have been generated.” As has been found in other research [19]–[21], [24], the results show that, in fact, students with SEN, according to the perception of a significant majority of teachers in this study, seem to have had greater socio-affective and emotional difficulties, in general, and depending on the type of diversity they presented. In this sense, positive teacher behavior should be emphasized so students perceive them as “credible” people, thus generating better learning environments and climates [68].

However, once again, it has been shown that teachers have not been providing a transversal educational response in the direction of emotional education so that students can recompose and regulate themselves after the crisis experienced. The present study showed that even though most teachers have the training, it does not seem sufficient to incorporate the essential elements of socioemotional competence in the curriculum in a cross-cutting manner. As pointed out by several studies [67], [69] in this “new reality,” in which the socio-emotional development of students urgently needs to be addressed, teachers with the proper qualities to exercise tutorial and guidance action in the classroom are required. That is, emotionally intelligent teachers are needed: teachers capable of being empathetic, with emotional maturity; teachers who integrate socio-emotional and emotional learning within the teaching-learning process; teachers who can regulate the positive and negative of their students. In addition, teachers should be trained, from an integrative approach, to support the return to social relationships at school, generating coexistence and positive interdependence that prevent possible relational imbalances such as isolation or school conflict [70].

In this line, addressing positive interpersonal management is imperative to avoid complicated socio-affective school situations [50], [71]–[73]. The need to invest in improving teacher training at all levels to provide them with new attitudes and methodological proposals is evident [9], [32]. This could help achieve coexistence levels that favor all students' school performance. As can be seen from the results of the present study, and in agreement with various authors [69]–[72], teachers must make the classroom and the school spaces for the socio-affective care of “all” the students.

In short, the results reflected the need to create a different proposal for inclusive innovation to address socioemotional education in the curriculum in a transversal, integrative, and structured way at the various levels of primary education. All the teachers and some specialists agreed to value the pedagogical model of educational psychomotor practice and the tools of corporal and artistic expression to support this program in the different subjects. These findings are present in other works [36]–[39], [58] in which physical activity is related to the improvement of emotional and cognitive development and learning processes. The design of strategies that include games that promote exercise and movement is recommended as an ideal form of stimulation. With these results, it was possible to design a project to improve the systematization of emotional education at school in post-pandemic times.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the information analyzed by the study's objectives, several fundamental conclusions have been drawn, which are crucial for designing an innovation project in emotional education in the post-pandemic period. The pandemic had a significant emotional and social impact on students from 1st to 6th grade in primary education, particularly affecting students with special educational needs. These students exhibited altered emotional states in the classroom at concerning levels and in ways atypical for their age. Emotions such as uncertainty, fear, sadness, anxiety, and isolation were direct consequences of the pandemic.

The study also found that emotions are not addressed in depth across all courses and subjects equally, nor are they integrated transversally within the curriculum. There is a clear need for more specialized training in emotional education for teachers, as their current training is limited and does not enable them to adequately respond to the emerging needs in classrooms after the pandemic. To address these issues, it is essential to reinforce emotional education and student socialization in the classroom, particularly through areas that enhance self-knowledge, self-regulation, and emotional expressiveness. Examples include psychomotor education, bodily expression, and artistic education.

The implications of this study highlight the need to review school practices, as the pandemic has revealed significant shortcomings in the holistic education of all students. Each educational center within the current school organization must identify those educational gaps that may affect the classroom climate and hinder the socio-emotional development of all students, particularly those with SEN. Moreover, each school's culture should promote a transversal and comprehensive emotional education to help bridge the gaps revealed by COVID-19. Each school can and should collaboratively engage in research-action processes that lead to innovation projects. These projects, in line with the findings presented here, should contribute to the development of full inclusion in educational institutions. This section is not mandatory but may be added if patents result from the work reported in this manuscript.

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